

LAYERED FINITE ELEMENT (FE) MODELLING OF CEMENT COMPOSITES COMBINING CONTINUOUS TEXTILES AND SYNTHETIC MICROFIBRES: A FLEXURAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This research presents a layered, semi-smear modelling approach for the prediction of the flexural response of Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) beams with combined continuous textiles (0.7v%) and short microfibres (1%). The constitutive behaviour of the composites was obtained from tensile experiments on TRC configurations and subsequently implemented in two different smearing approaches. The first approach concentrated the cross-sectional resistance in the load-bearing textile layers, whereas the second distributed the contribution of the short microfibres over the entire thickness. A satisfactory agreement was obtained between the experimental results and both numerical approaches, however, the distributed approach slightly underestimated the flexural response of the material.

KEYWORDS

Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) composites; Finite Element (FE) modelling; Flexural simulation; Semi-smear approach

INTRODUCTION

Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) composites can provide a promising alternative to conventional structural elements in applications where high tuneability, slenderness and freedom-of-form are required (Bentur & Mindess, 2006; Peled et al., 2017). The feasibility of TRCs in load-bearing applications has been highlighted in literature, ranging from efficient shell structures (Hegger et al., 2008; Scholzen et al., 2015; Tysmans et al., 2009; Verwimp et al., 2015), sandwich panels (Shams et al., 2014; Vervloet et al., 2019) to pedestrian bridges (Helbig et al., 2016).

The modelling of TRCs can be classified in two main categories: discrete and smeared modelling approaches. Discrete modelling approaches require the different TRC components to be implemented separately, with their intrinsic geometrical and constitutive features, as well as a thorough characterization of the bond properties (Bertolesi et al., 2014; Chudoba et al., 2004; Djamai et al., 2017; Mazzucco et al., 2018). Provided that these primary features and parameters can be identified in a satisfactory way, discrete modelling approaches allow for a high level of accuracy, however at an elevated computational cost. In case the textile reinforcement is distributed evenly throughout the TRC section, smeared modelling approaches, based on micromechanical models, can offer a satisfactory modelling alternative at a low computational cost (Chudoba et al., 2016; Colombo et al., 2015; Verwimp et al., 2015; Williams Portal et al., 2013; Wozniak et al., 2017).

A recent alternative has been presented in the form of semi-smear modelling approaches, which allow to model TRCs as a discrete stack of smeared layers with constitutively unique mechanical features (Chudoba et al., 2019; El Kadi et al., 2018a, 2021a). The use of semi-smear modelling approaches is particularly proficient for the modelling of non-homogeneously stacked textile reinforcement layers in TRCs, as is e.g. the case when using open, 3D textile reinforcement systems (El Kadi et al., 2019, 2020; Haik et al., 2017). Indeed, a fully smeared approach, that assumes identical constitutive properties over

the cross-sectional height, would be incapable to correctly capture the intrinsic flexural lever arm of discretely distributed reinforcement layers.

The use of 3D, open textile reinforcement structures in TRCs offer multiple advantages, such as manufacturing ease and an improved mechanical response in flexural applications (El Kadi et al., 2019; Haik et al., 2014). At the same time, the open reinforcement structures can lead to low reinforcement levels (fibre volume fraction V_f) and hence intrinsically fewer and larger cracks. In literature, the use of additional short microfibres, on top of the continuous textile reinforcement systems, has been explored to improve the crack formation of these materials (Gielis, El Kadi, Tysmans, et al., 2023a). The modelling of 3D TRCs containing additional short microfibres has however not yet been performed in literature and is the purpose of the proposed study.

The research presented in this article presents a semi-smear modelling approach for 3D TRCs containing additional short microfibres. A numerical campaign is presented and validated on four-point bending experimental results obtained from (Gielis, El Kadi, Tysmans, et al., 2023b). A comparison is drawn between a reference 3D TRC and a 3D TRC with added microfibres. In all cases, the flexural predictions are based on the constitutive behaviour of identical TRC configurations, obtained from tensile experiments (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023). Two distinct approaches are proposed to implement the short microfibres in the semi-smear layers. A first approach consists in concentrating the entire cross-sectional resistance (of both the continuous textiles and the short microfibres) in the load-bearing layers. The second approach distributes the effect of the short fibres over the entire cross-sectional thickness.

The article starts with an overview of the tensile experimental data, obtained from (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023), as well as a description of the numerical features employed in this study. Subsequently, the numerical results are presented and validated with flexural experimental results.

TENSILE EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Materials

Textiles and short fibres

For all materials commercially available alternatives were selected. A detailed description can be found in (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023). The used 3D textiles contained two planar, AR-glass reinforcement layers, separated over a distance of 8.5 mm by knitted, polyester connections (SitGrid 701, Wilhelm Kneitz AG, Germany) (see Figure 1 (a)). The 2400 tex fibre bundles were arranged in a mesh size of 22.5 mm by 22.5 mm. The textiles were SBR coated with an uncoated density of 536 g/m² and a coated density of 616 g/m².

The short fibres were commercially available polypropylene (PP) fibres with a length of 6 mm (Redco, Belgium) (see Figure 1 (b)).

Figure 1: (a) Picture of 3D textile reinforcement (b) 6 mm length polypropylene (PP) fibres.

Cementitious matrix

The matrix was composed of Portland cement (CEM I 52.2 N, Holcim, Belgium), fly ash (Microsit, BauMineral GmbH, Germany), quartz sand (M34, Sibelco, Belgium), water and superplasticizer (MasterGlenium 51, BASF, Netherlands).

TRC coupons

The effective fibre volume fraction (V_f) in loading direction of the continuous textiles was 0.7 % and of the microfibres 1 %. All TRC coupons had dimensions of 500 mm x 60 mm x 15 mm and a mortar cover thickness of 2 mm. After casting, the samples were cured at room temperature for 28 days and a speckle pattern was applied for the Digital Image Correlation (DIC).

Tensile experimental campaign

The input of the semi-smear model was obtained from two tensile campaigns on (i) 3D TRCs samples and (ii) 3D TRC samples with additional microfibres. The experimental campaigns are described in detail in (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023). A full-field assessment of the displacements and strains was obtained through DIC analysis. The tensile test campaign was performed according to RILEM recommendation TC 232-TDT (RILEM Technical Committee 232-TDT (Wolfgang Brameshuber) et al., 2016).

The obtained experimental curves (from (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023)) that were used as an input for the numerical models in this study are reported in Figure 2 for completeness. Table 1 provides an overview of the obtained tensile constitutive properties that were used as an input for the flexural numerical simulations ($\sigma_{c/f}$ = matrix cracking/failure stress, $E_{1/3}$ = pre-/post-cracking stiffness). A clear improvement in mechanical response was observed for the 3D TRCs containing microfibres when compared to the reference 3D alternatives without microfibres. The numerical model, described in the following section, used this tensile experimental data as input to predict differences in the flexural behaviour of these TRC configurations.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves obtained from DIC analysis of (a) 3D TRCs (3D) and (b) 3D TRCs with added microfibres (3D+PP).

Table 1: Tensile experimental results, obtained from (Gielis, El Kadi, Snoeck, et al., 2023).

Conf.	σ_c [MPa]	E_1 [MPa]	σ_f [MPa]	E_3 [MPa]
3D	2.19	9442.73	4.24	73.45
3D + PP	2.26	13456.55	5.27	117.98

NUMERICAL MODEL

Theoretical considerations

The numerical model presented in this study is based on a layered, semi-smear modelling approach where the TRC cross-section is subdivided as a stack of individual smeared layers with independent constitutive properties (El Kadi et al., 2018b). The constitutive behaviour of each layer was attributed

with respect to the actual material present at the respective cross-sectional height and followed the following assumptions:

Composite layup

Each layer was attributed a unique constitutive behaviour, obtained from the tensile properties of the entire TRC section in tension. The layup was constructed based on the actual layup of the TRCs. In this case, the TRCs contained one 3D textile with two load-bearing textile layers and a mortar cover of 2 mm at the top and bottom. Hence, the layup contained five layers, as depicted in Figure 3. In the model, the position and thickness of the individual layers followed the geometrical features of the TRC (see Figure 3 (a)). The textile layers were given the actual thickness of the textile reinforcement (1.25 mm) but assumed a smeared distribution of the load-bearing properties over the entire layer. It was assumed that the bond properties between the TRC constituents were intrinsically present in the tensile constitutive behaviour. Hence, in the model, the bond between the individual layers was assumed perfect.

Layer	Thickness (mm)
Mortar	2
Textile	1.25
Mortar	8.5
Textile	1.25
Mortar	2

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Example of a layered-wise stacking of smeared layers to represent the mortar (blue) and textile reinforcement (orange) throughout the cross-section.

Tensile properties of the textile layers

The constitutive behaviour of the textile reinforcement was obtained from the tensile experimental data (see Table 1). The constitutive behaviour of the textile layers was assumed as linear. Furthermore, the additional post-cracking resistance of the TRCs was assumed to be carried by the textile layers. Hence, the experimentally obtained post-cracking stiffness E_3 (of the entire cross-section) was rescaled by the ratio between the total thickness and the textile layers ($15 \text{ mm} / 2.5 \text{ mm} = 6$).

Tensile properties of the mortar layers

In tension, the mortar layers were assumed to only contribute to the uncracked zone of the TRC's constitutive behaviour. In the post-cracking stage, these layers were assumed to provide no further contribution and to remain at the stress level of matrix cracking.

Compressive properties of all the layers

In compression, a linear constitutive behaviour was attributed to all layers, following the mortar properties, obtained from (Gielis, El Kadi, Tysmans, et al., 2023b).

Influence of short microfibres

Two different approaches were followed to account for the mechanical contributions observed in the TRC configurations containing short microfibres.

The first approach assumed the entire post-cracking resistance of the 3D+PP TRCs to be concentrated in the load-bearing textile layers. In this consideration, the experimentally obtained E_3 for the 3D+PP configurations (117.98 MPa) was entirely considered in the rescaling and the textile layers were given a post-cracking stiffness of 707.88 MPa ($= 117.98 \text{ MPa} * 6$). Physically, this consideration assumed that the presence of microfibres mainly contributed to the anchorage of the load-bearing textile layers in the TRC and hence that their contribution was mainly notable at these cross-sectional lever arms.

The second approach distributed the influence of the short microfibres over the entire cross-sectional height. Therefore, the textile layers in the 3D+PP configuration were given the same constitutive

behaviour as the textile layers in the 3D configuration. The difference in stiffness between both configurations was however implemented in the mortar layers (after rescaling). Physically, this consideration assumed a separate contribution towards the constitutive response of respectively the continuous 3D textiles and the short microfibres.

It is important to note that both considerations were entirely equivalent in tension, since the total capacity of all layers remained the same. In flexural considerations however, the lever arm of the respective layers plays an important role in the mechanical response of the section.

Implemented constitutive behaviour

Following the assumptions provided in the previous section, Figure 4 gives a comparative overview of the constitutive behaviours implemented in this study for the different TRCs configurations (a) 3D, (b) 3D+PP(concentrated) and (c) 3D+PP(distributed).

Figure 4: Considered configurations in numerical model with (a) 3D configuration, (b) 3D+PP configuration, assuming the contribution from the microfibres concentrated in the textile layers, (c) 3D+PP configuration, assuming the contribution from the microfibres distributed over the cross-sectional height and (d) overview of all inputted constitutive behaviours.

Flexural numerical implementation

The four-point bending, semi-smear composite model presented in this study was implemented in numerical software Abaqus (Dassault Systèmes Simulia, 2012) through a five-layer composite layup assigned to a continuum shell element. The Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) material model available in Abaqus was used to implement the different material constitutive behaviours. The CDP parameters were taken as their default values, in accordance with (Häußler-Combe & Hartig, 2007; Ohno & Hannant, 1994). The selected continuum shell mesh elements were SC8R 8-node quadrilateral in-plane mesh elements. During meshing, a singular mesh element over the composite thickness was guaranteed to warrant a correct assignment of the composite layup over the cross-sectional height.

In the flexural campaign, the TRC beams had dimensions of 500 mm x 60 mm x 15 mm. The distance between the supports and loading pins was respectively 350 mm and 100 mm. Figure 5 presents a graphical visualization of the TRC beam, loading pins and support line (highlighted in red). Symmetry boundary conditions were attributed to all elements in the longitudinal and width direction. Furthermore, the vertical translational degree of freedom of the support lines was restricted. The interaction properties between the loading pins (cylindrical rigid body) and the top surface of the TRC

beams were defined as frictionless and hard contact in respectively the tangential and perpendicular direction.

Figure 5: Graphical depiction of numerical model of four-point bending test.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND VALIDATION WITH FLEXURAL EXPERIMENTS

Load – displacement curves

This section compares the numerically obtained load – displacement curves with the flexural experimental data from (Gielis, El Kadi, Tysmans, et al., 2023b). The flexural tests were performed on 3D and 3D+PP TRC coupons of 500 mm x 60 mm x 15 mm (6 specimens per configuration). The distance between the supports and loading pins was respectively 350 mm and 100 mm.

3D TRCs

Figure 6 presents a comparison between the numerical simulations and flexural experimental results obtained for the 3D TRC configuration ((a) in Figure 4). Since this configuration did not contain any short microfibres, it mainly served as a validation of the semi-smeared modelling approach, as presented in (El Kadi et al., 2018b) and (El Kadi et al., 2021b). When comparing the numerical simulations with the experimental results, a satisfactory agreement was observed in the pre- and post-cracking stage of the mechanical response. The post-cracking flexural stiffness of the material was correctly predicted by the model at 6.01 N/mm.

Figure 6: Comparison of numerical simulations with flexural experimental results of 3D TRC configuration.

Figure 7 presents the distribution of the principal (longitudinal) stresses in both the top and bottom textile load bearing layers at 30 mm displacement. Tensile stresses are observed in both layers, meaning

that the neutral axis of the cross-section has shifted upwards to the top mortar cover layer. A clearly higher tensile stress uptake is observed in the bottom layer (maximally 13.13 MPa vs 1.80 MPa), which reflects the higher distance with respect to the neutral axis.

Figure 7: Longitudinal (principal) stress distribution in load-bearing layers at 30 mm displacement (a) in the top textile layer and (b) in the bottom textile layer.

3D+PP TRCs

Figure 8 shows a comparison between the numerical simulations and flexural experimental results obtained for the 3D+PP TRC configuration ((b) and (c) in Figure 4). The numerical approach “Num. sim. 3D+PP (conc.)” in Figure 8 assumed that the presence of microfibres mainly contributed to the anchorage of the load-bearing textile layers in the TRC and hence that their contribution was mainly notable at these cross-sectional lever arms (configuration (b) in Figure 4). The approach corresponding with “Num. sim. 3D+PP (distr.)” distributed the influence of the short microfibres over the entire cross-sectional height (configuration (c) in Figure 4). Figure 8 shows that the concentrated approach achieved a satisfactory prediction of the global constitutive behaviour of the material, whereas the distributed approach slightly underestimated the flexural stiffness on the post-cracking stage. The obtained post-cracking stiffness for the concentrated and distributed approach were respectively 10.09 MPa and 9.06 MPa, or a relative difference of approximately 10 %.

Figure 8: Comparison of numerical simulations with flexural experimental results of 3D+PP TRC configuration.

These preliminary numerical results indicated that the mechanical, macroscopic contribution of the additional short fibres in 3D TRCs could be superior at the (cross-sectional) position of the continuous, longitudinal 3D reinforcement. When superimposing the constitutive behaviour of the short microfibres in the whole cross-section (Num. sim. 3D+PP (distr.)), the experimentally observed flexural response could not fully be achieved. Thus meaning that the added microfibres serve as additional anchors for the continuous load-bearing layers, on top of the cross-sectional resistance they provide on their own. At the same time, these assumptions should be further investigated as the differences remain low and there is yet no clear indication that the activation of the short microfibres can be assumed the same in tensile and flexural loading conditions (as was the case for the continuous microfibres). This remains the subject of future studies.

Stress and strain distributions over the TRC height

Figure 9 presents the numerical through-thickness stress and strain evolutions of (a) the 3D, (b) the 3D+PP(conc.) and (c) 3D+PP(distr.) TRC configurations at a representative midspan displacement of 30 mm. The strain evolutions followed, as expected, a linear behaviour over the cross-sectional height. The stress evolutions followed the constitutive behaviour of the respective layers and exhibited clear stress peaks at the position of the textile reinforcement (the layups are plotted transparently under the evolutions for visualization purposes). At 30 mm displacement, all configurations had the neutral axis of the cross-section shifted to the top mortar cover layer, at approximately 13 mm cross-sectional height.

The 3D+PP(conc.) configuration clearly exhibited a larger stress peak in the bottom load-bearing layer compared to the 3D and 3D+PP(distr.) alternatives. This follows the inputted tensile constitutive behaviour as expected (see Figure 4 (d)). At the same time, the 3D+PP(distr.) configuration exhibited a linear increase in stress level in the mortar layers, following the inputted mortar properties with added microfibres (see Figure 4 (d)).

(a) – 3D

(b) – 3D+PP(conc.)

(c) – 3D+PP(distr.)

Figure 9: Numerical through-thickness stress and strain evolutions of (a) the 3D, (b) the 3D+PP(conc.) and (c) 3D+PP(distr.) TRC configurations at a midspan displacement of 30 mm.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a semi-smear numerical modelling approach for 3D TRCs with short microfibres. Two different configurations were compared: one reference 3D configuration and one configuration with added short microfibres (3D+PP). Tensile experiments on TRC coupons provided the input data for the four-point bending numerical model.

Numerically, two different approaches were followed to implement the 3D+PP configurations: the first approach concentrated the tensile constitutive behaviour of the short microfibres at the cross-sectional height of the continuous textile reinforcement (3D+PP(conc.)), the second assumed an even distribution of the short microfibres over the height (3D+pp(distr.)). Both numerical approaches provided a satisfactory prediction of the flexural experimental data, however, the first 3D+PP(conc.) approach gave the best prediction with a post-cracking stiffness of approximately 10 % higher than the 3D+PP(distr.) approach. Additionally, the numerical through-thickness stress and strain evolutions of all the modelled configurations was discussed in this study.

The numerical results presented in this work offer a validation of the computationally inexpensive semi-smear modelling approach for the modelling of 3D TRCs containing microfibres. Future research should investigate the validity of the approach in larger and more complex (shells, curved elements, etc.) structures with potentially uneven distribution of the microfibres.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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